

CAUSES OF BURNOUT SYNDROME AND COPING STRATEGIES AMONG NURSES

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***Abstract.** Socio-political and socio-economic changes promote new working conditions that certainly affect the psychological and somatic state of the individual. This has led to physical and emotional exhaustion among workers resulting in excessive accumulation of workload and high burnout levels.*

Burnout syndrome is the continuous exposure to work-stress associated with working conditions, in which pleasure and work performance decrease. Emotional burnout syndrome is a form of occupational disease that not only destroys a person's professional activity, but also causes psychosomatic illnesses.

The greatest danger of burnout is that it develops almost imperceptibly and if you ignore its first signs, the satisfaction with professional activities will decrease with each passing day.

Burnout descriptions can be found in the historical record and they appear to be apparent across different times and cultures. However, it was not until the mid 1970s that researchers have started investigating burnout feelings: Herbert Freudenberger, a psychiatrist, and Christina Maslach, a social psychologist, were the first researchers who began examining burnout.

In the health area, nursing stands out as one of the most exhausting professions owing to different circumstances in professional practice causing physical and emotional exhaustion. It is common to find burnout syndrome in health professionals, especially in the field of nursing.

In this article, we discuss job burnout, list cause and symptoms of burnout, show what it looks like and offer some tips you can incorporate into your workflow to help you reduce and overcome burnout symptoms. The article focuses on the study of the syndrome, because despite the fact that the phenomenon has been studied for more than thirty years, there are many theories and controversies about its origin and affiliation.

According to this more studies in investigation of individual, psychological and organizational factors of burnout is necessary. Also a development of preventive program to reduce burnout is needed.

Keywords: *burnout syndrome, depersonalization, risk factors, nursing.*

Introduction. One of the most common psychological symptoms modern people increasingly experience is burnout, i.e., the outcome of chronic, work-related stress. The problem of burnout results from the importance that modern society assigns to work and its derivatives. It is often a consequence of excessive professional involvement along with the lack of positive feedback from the environment.

The very term “burnout” accurately reflects the essence of exhaustion experienced by an individual as a result of highly stressful working conditions [1, 2].

History of the term “burnout”. What do we know about burnout, and what can we do about it? Burnout descriptions can be found in the historical record and they appear to be apparent across different times and cultures.

Burnout as a phenomenon has probably existed at all times and in all cultures. Those interested in literature will find descriptions of what we now call burnout going back as far as the Old Testament (Exodus 18: 17–18). Pastors speak of the

“weariness of Elijah” [3]. In Thomas Mann’s great novel *Buddenbrooks*, too, we recognize the matter under discussion here in the figure of Thomas Buddenbrook. The verb “to burn out” is used by Shakespeare at the end of the sixteenth century [4, 5].

The concept of burnout was first introduced by Fredeunberger in 1974. Fredeunberger had stated that burnout occurred more commonly in occupations whose members directly work with people. It was during this period that hypotheses began to emerge on the increase in pressures and, consequently, labor stress, especially in health professionals, such as doctors, nurses, and nursing technicians [6].

The definition of burnout in Mosby's dictionary is as follows: “Burnout is a popular term for the condition of having mental or physical energy depletion after a period of chronic unrelieved job-related stress characterized sometimes by physical illness” [7].

In the 1980s, psychologists Cristina Maslach and Susan Jackson began to study the emotions of health professionals in the work environment and defined “burnout” as physical and emotional fatigue resulting in a decrease or loss of motivation for work that can evolve to total exhaustion and a sense of failure [8].

Maslach and Jackson (1981) divided the concept of burnout into three categories, namely emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (DP) and lack of personal accomplishment (PA). They stated that exhaustion results from decrease or loss of self-confidence and interest in one's profession as well as feelings of fatigue and weakness. By measuring individuals across these three themes, it may be possible to identify the presence of burnout and, going further, examine the contributing factors [9]. According to the World Health Organization, burnout is an occupational phenome [10].

It is not specific to nursing: Professionals in any industry, from teaching to engineering, can suffer from this type of exhaustion caused by unrealistic expectations, lack of sleep, and other work-related stressors. However, due to their

high-stress work environment, nurses and other medical professionals face a greater risk of burnout.

What is nurse burnout?

Burnout is a common psychological phenomenon among nurses. It is characterized by a decline in physical, emotional, and psychological energy resulting from work-related stress that leads to cynicism toward clients and colleagues and feelings of low self-efficacy [11]. Burnout may arise because of work overload; a lack of resources, control, and justice; value conflicts; and the absence of a sense of community [12].

Burnout includes 3 key aspects:

- Emotional Exhaustion (EE): the state of being physically and emotionally exhausted by work stress, which is characterized by low energy, fatigue, depression, hopelessness, and helplessness.

- Depersonalization (DP): the interpersonal aspect of burnout that manifests in unfeeling, negative behaviors toward others, and detachment from caring and instructions.

- Low Personal Accomplishment (PA): the state of negatively evaluating ones'self as being incompetent, unsuccessful, and inadequate; consequently, employees exhibit low levels of contribution to their work. [9, 11, 12, 13].

Generally, this term is associated with work-related stressors from situations such as the following:

- absence of a sense of community;
- a lack of resources, control, and justice;
- compassion fatigue;
- inadequate or ineffective management and leadership;
- longer shifts, or working more than 40 hours per week;
- sleep deprivation;
- value conflicts;
- work overload;

- working in a hospital setting or high-stress environment [11, 12].

Symptoms

The symptomatology of burnout proves, on close inspection, to be extremely complex; after all, the syndrome has now been described in around 60 professions and groups of people.

Signs of burnout can be separated into 3 categories:

Physical:

- low energy; feeling tired and easily fatigued much of the time;
- frequent illness;
- frequent headaches, back pain, or muscle aches and pains;
- change in appetite or sleep habits.

Emotional:

- chronic feelings of self-doubt; sense of failure;
- loss of motivation; decreased satisfaction;
- feeling defeated and alone in the world;
- feeling cynical and bitter about life.

Behavioral:

- substance abuse or dependency;
- being irritable around others;
- isolating oneself from others;
- withdrawing from responsibilities;
- putting off getting things done.

What can you do to manage nurse burnout?

In order to avert multifactorial burnout, health promotion should be started early, relaxation techniques, regular breaks, part-time working, reduction in bureaucratic processes [14, 15, 16].

Take care of yourself first. The only person who can make sure that your emotional and physical needs are met is *you*.

Here are a few simple ways nurses can practice self-care regularly:

- *Exercise:* Nurses who exercise are better able to handle the stamina required in many healthcare facilities. In addition, regular movement will help you manage stress levels and prevent comorbidities such as high blood pressure and diabetes.

- *Meditate:* Mindfulness practice or meditation can help nurses and nursing students manage burnout, chronic stress, anxiety, and overall sense of well-being.

- *Make the Most of Your Time Off.* Step away from work and focus on recharging. Spending time with supportive people, laughing, doing something creative, and making time for fun are all great ways to recharge. It's important to truly take a break from the stressors, to step away and focus on other things. This can be easier said than done for someone who is used to focusing on work!

- *Get Enough Sleep.* Insomnia and lack of sleep are a vicious cycle. When someone lays awake at night stressed and worried, this causes the body to release more stress hormones. More stress hormones lead to chronic stress, which over time can become burnout. Getting plenty of rest is critical for mental, emotional, and physical health. Practice good sleep hygiene and consider a soothing nighttime routine like gentle stretching, reading, or meditation.

- *Eat Healthy Food.* Mental and physical health are interconnected, and good nutrition can make a difference. Healthy food can increase energy and boost mood, which can lead to an overall more positive outlook and lower burnout risk. The Mediterranean Diet and mindful eating practices have both been empirically proven to be protective factors against burnout [17-22].

Conclusions. Preventing and reducing work related burnout is of great importance not only with regard to the quality of life of those affected or endangered, but also for preventing the economic losses which come about as a result of absenteeism and job turnover.

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